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Information Discovery with Financial Data Mining

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Abstract –

In this study, a data mining application was applied to the credit monitoring processes of a private financial institution's customers. With this application, it is aimed to determine the customers with high accuracy and common points. The reason why the legal follow-up customers are trying to be estimated is that these customers do not make their payments in a timely manner and are the class that left the firm in the most difficult position. The estimated damage to the firm can be minimized. In this study conducted in the banking sector, the classification of the data mining methods and the analysis of existing individual loan customers and the inference of the future payment status of potential customers are aimed. For this purpose, the demographic information of the customers was obtained from the company and the tables were prepared by arranging the data. Customers are classified as those who are not following legal proceedings and those who do not go to the problem data mining classification model. In order to solve this problem, C5.0, C&RT, QUEST and CHAID algorithms were chosen from the algorithms of the classification model. In the study, IBM SPSS Modeler was used as data mining and an application was made for the evaluation of individual loan customers.

Keywords – Banking sector, Loan Customers, Forecasting, Data Mining, Classification, C5.0, C&RT, QUEST, CHAID

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, investment projects for transformational information technologies for different technologies in the finance sector, energy sector, health sector, telecom sector and public institutions have started to increase rapidly. There is a need for these technologies to reach their corporate goals, to increase customer satisfaction and to configure data centers to meet their business needs. The amount of data is increasing day by day and with the increasing amount of data, companies are trying to use the data effectively to obtain information. As a result of increasing competition conditions and developing computer technologies, information that will provide advantages for companies is gaining importance [1].

Data mining methods are widely used in order to obtain previously known, valid and applicable information stored in financial data heaps [2].

In his research, Özekeş formed the data set of the application between 1993 - 1998 by a Czech Bank. The data set was taken from the internet. It consists of 8 tables describing the Bank's customers, their accounts, transactions, payment orders, loans granted and credit cards. The aim of this study is to use a decision tree technique. Using the data set to estimate which customers can or cannot repay the credits they receive. In this way, it is also possible to estimate whether the loan will be eligible for the customer requesting a new loan. It was observed that 11% of the loans received in the data set were not repaid [3].

In the study conducted by Çalış in the banking sector, the study included data mining application to evaluate the repayment performances of customers using personal bank loans. Clustering and classification of data mining methods

and the analysis of existing individual loan customers and the inference of payment status of future potential customers are aimed. The CHAID algorithm has been found to provide the best result with a correct recording rate of 95.5%. An even higher estimation success was achieved by identifying and subtracting outliers and increasing the decision tree level [4].

In the study on cluster analysis as a tool for the oversight of banks performed by Doğan, the clustering analysis was applied based on the financial ratios of the commercial banks operating in the Turkish Banking Sector (1998-2006). In the light of the results obtained by discussing the results of the application with the financial analysis results of banks, the clustering analysis technique was examined as a complementary technique to the existing techniques used in the supervision of banks in order to determine the financial performance of banks and to identify financially similar banks [5].

Akın has implemented an application to decide whether to provide loans to companies working with Koç Group. When the customers are evaluated, the information they have filled in the data warehouse is collected, arranged and classified. It has been observed that the rate of entering the legal follow-up process of credit requests, which were accepted after the decisions taken with the restructured credit acceptance rules using data mining, decreased. [6].

According to the credit card expenditures, the data mining application was determined by Parman. Parman conducted customer segmentation and risk valuation analyzes on the data of 1704 credit card customers belonging to a single branch of a medium-sized bank from private banks. He used discriminant analysis from data mining methods. In this study, it has been tried to determine the areas where credit card holders differ from each other according to their spending characteristics. As a result of the analysis, a meaningful model

has been introduced that distinguishes gold and classic credit card customers according to their spending characteristics [7].

In their study, Hsia et al. used a data mining technique to analyze course preferences and course completion rates at a university in Taiwan. The aim of the studies is to use the data mining technique to determine the course preferences of the students and the course preferences of the students who are continuing their education. Decision trees were used to find the students' course preferences, to determine the correlation between the link analysis course category and the participant profession, and the decision forest was used to find the participants the possibility of completing their preferred course. Chaid was used as a decision tree. As a result, high estimation success was achieved [8].

Farquad, Ravi and Raju propose a hybrid method that uses a combination of Support Vector Machine and Naive Bayes methods to estimate bank credit card customer loss rates. A data set consisting of 6.89% of lost customers was used in the study. 68.52% of the correct classification rules have been obtained [9].

The study, conducted by Old et al., gender officers in credit card usage habits in Turkey, marital status, age, education level, monthly income amount, studied the relationship between demographic characteristics such as some individuals in the family. While there was no relationship between gender, marital status, child ownership, number of individuals in the family and credit card expenditures, they found a significant relationship between monthly income, number of credit cards, education level and age and credit card expenditures [10].

In the data mining study on personnel selection and performance evaluation in the banking sector performed by Bilen, the performances of the employees working in the banking sector were evaluated and the clustering methods were categorized according to the performance success levels of the personnel with the K means. The resulting performance levels were then used as an output to form classification rules and decision rules. Data mining classification algorithms have been used by taking into consideration the employees' demographic information such as age, marital status, gender, educational status, foreign language, branch of work and position in business life. According to the WEKA outputs, the ID3 algorithm provided the best results regarding the misclassified recording rate and the mean absolute error and the results of the ID3 algorithm were emphasized. With the decision rules obtained by decision tree algorithms, performance success levels of personnel in each province have been determined [11].

In the study of customer loss analysis in credit cards by using data mining techniques, Tosun will examine the various qualifications of Yapı Kredi Bank's credit card customers and try to reveal the profile of a lost customer through data mining methods. In the study, decision trees method was used. When the threshold value of decision trees is used, the number of qualifications used decreases, the last account transaction date is 12 months, if the customer has not made any purchases in the last 3 months, the probability of general loss is quite high; If the customer has lost the possibility of being lost, the results have been reached [12].

In the study on the comparison of classification methods in data mining performed by Çakır, all stages of the data mining standard process were applied on a randomly selected dataset from the banking customer database and the classification function of data mining was emphasized. The application is

based on the comparison of these techniques using multiple classification techniques on multiple dependent variables. Therefore, regression analysis, artificial neural networks and C5.0 decision rule derivation algorithm are determined as the classification techniques to be used in practice. In the evaluation made regarding velocity criterion, the C5.0 algorithm has been found to be unquestionably advantageous [13].

In a study conducted by Aşan et al., the bank carried out a study to examine the socio-economic characteristics of customers using a credit card with a clustering analysis in order to identify certain customer patterns by providing better recognition to customers. In these clusters, customers are also grouped according to variables such as gender, age, marital status, education, occupation, income level credit card type. It was found that the customers in these three clusters differed according to socio-economic variables [14].

Biçer aims to evaluate the credit demands of a bank's retail banking department for debt consolidation and housing renewal by applying data mining techniques and to accept or reject the loan requests. 13 variables of 5960 customers were used in the data set. The loan request assessment application was implemented with SAS Enterprise Miner 4.2 package program. Clients were grouped according to their loyalty ratings by clustering analysis and 4 groups emerged [15].

Data mining in banking; creation of loyal customer portfolio, determination of credit card fraud, determination of customer groups based on credit card expenditures, evaluation of credit demands, control of credit repayments, increasing sales amount to unit customers with cross-selling, creation of customer specific sales policies, determination of risky customer types, determination of insurance fraud, determination of new policies.

In this study, a data mining application was carried out with the data obtained from a bank operating in Turkey. The Bank's data is based on age, gender, marital status, educational status, monthly income, home, vehicle, having children, spouse income, payment status, bank salary, and work. In practice, it was ensured that the existing customers were evaluated by classification analysis. Then, decision tree algorithms were used to classify customers according to their payment status, and inferences were made for future potential customers. In this process, IBM SPSS Modeler, a data mining program that allows us to reach the hidden patterns in the data in a short time by using classification algorithms was used.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The system included a data mining application for the evaluation of loan repayment performance of individual credit customers in the first-class branch of a private bank in 2015. Since lending is risky for banks, it is aimed to obtain information through data mining from existing data to minimize the risk ratio in decision making in this study. The data used in the application consists of the legal follow-up and normal payment records of the individual credit customers.

Data were transferred to Excel and preprocessed. Then, the data was transferred to IBM SPSS Modeler and the data was cleaned and prepared. The information of 226 customer records was used. In practice, the classification of data mining methods is included. In the application of classification, decision tree algorithms are applied, and it is aimed to make rules for future customers.

IBM SPSS Modeler uses some methods to prepare the data for modeling. Clementine is an open solution when accessing data. It can easily connect to all ODBC-compliant database data and can be used without changing the format of the data. Free and ASCII format data can be retrieved easily with SPSS and SAS data [1].

If the credit card is not paid in full or the minimum payment is due until the due date, the card delay starts. On the 15th day after the due date, your credit card is temporarily closed until the minimum payment amount has been paid. When the credit card debt enters a 90-day delay period, the card is canceled and defined as the Legal Follow-up process. The payment status of the customers who did not interfere with the loan payments is called normal payment credit.

The purpose of the application is grouped according to the payment performance of the customers, determining the factors that affect the credit repayments, and accordingly, the ability to make individual loans and other products of the bank as well as the cross-selling according to the customer groups. In practice, it is aimed to determine the products to be sold for existing customers and to make rules for the customers to be used in the future.

A. Collection of data

At this stage, according to the customer numbers from the related departments of the bank, the information of 226 customers with total follow-up and normal payment for the last five months was obtained.

B. Clearing data

Improperly entered noise is defined as clearing of data, extreme values, missing or incorrect data.

Field	Type	Outliers	Extremes	Action	Impute Missing	Method	% Complete	Valid Records
Cinsiyet	Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226
Medeni_Hal	Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226
Yas	Ordered Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226
Aylik_Gelir	Ordered Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226
Es_Gelir	Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226
Ev	Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226
Arac	Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226
Cocuk	Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226
Banka_Muassas	Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226
Calisma_Du	Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226
Ogrenim_Du	Ordered Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226
Odeme	Set	--	---	Never	Filed		100	226

Fig. 1 Process of clearing data's

When we look at the outliers and extremes of the data in the given tables, we see that our data is quite clean, and the data is 100% full and there is no lost data.

C. Conversion of data

“Age” and “Monthly income” are categorized due to a large number of uses at this stage.

Age: The smallest age is 23, the highest age is 71. It has been categorized at times.

Table 1. Age variable range

Age	23	30	37	44	51	58	Above
Category	-	-	-	-	-	-	66
	29	36	43	50	57	65	

Monthly Income: The lowest income is 950 ₺ and the highest income is 6028₺. The categorical status is shown Table 2.

Table 2. Monthly income variable

Monthly Income	950	1701	2251	2651	3351	Above 4201
	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1700	2250	2650	3350	4200	

Looking at the data we have the smallest and highest monthly income and age distribution, Table 1 above and Table 2 it was formed. The following Table 3 shows the edited data.

Table 3. Part of the edited data table

Cinsiyet	Medeni_Hal	Yas	Aylik_gelir	Es_geliri	Ev	Arac	Cocuk	Banka_Muassas	Calisma_Durumu	Ogrenim_Durumu	Odeme
KADIN	BEKAR	44-50	950-1700	VAR	VAR	YOK	YOK	HAYIR	KAMU	LISE	KANUNI TAKIP
KADIN	EVLI	44-50	950-1700	VAR	VAR	YOK	VAR	HAYIR	OZEL	ILKOGRETIM	KANUNI TAKIP
ERKEK	EVLI	44-50	950-1700	YOK	VAR	YOK	VAR	EVET	KAMU	ILKOGRETIM	KANUNI TAKIP
ERKEK	EVLI	44-50	2251-2650	YOK	YOK	YOK	VAR	EVET	KAMU	ILKOGRETIM	KANUNI TAKIP
ERKEK	EVLI	30-36	950-1700	YOK	YOK	YOK	VAR	HAYIR	OZEL	LISE	KANUNI TAKIP
ERKEK	EVLI	44-50	950-1700	YOK	VAR	YOK	VAR	HAYIR	KAMU	ILKOGRETIM	KANUNI TAKIP
ERKEK	EVLI	51-57	950-1700	YOK	YOK	YOK	VAR	EVET	EMEKLI	LISE	KANUNI TAKIP
KADIN	BEKAR	33-39	950-1700	YOK	YOK	YOK	VAR	HAYIR	OZEL	LISE	KANUNI TAKIP
KADIN	BEKAR	44-50	2251-2650	YOK	YOK	YOK	VAR	HAYIR	KAMU	LISE	KANUNI TAKIP
ERKEK	EVLI	44-50	1701-2250	YOK	VAR	YOK	VAR	EVET	KAMU	ILKOGRETIM	KANUNI TAKIP
ERKEK	EVLI	37-43	950-1700	YOK	YOK	YOK	VAR	HAYIR	OZEL	LISE	KANUNI TAKIP
ERKEK	BEKAR	37-43	950-1700	YOK	YOK	YOK	VAR	HAYIR	OZEL	ILKOGRETIM	KANUNI TAKIP
ERKEK	EVLI	37-43	950-1700	YOK	YOK	YOK	VAR	HAYIR	OZEL	LISE	KANUNI TAKIP
ERKEK	BEKAR	37-43	950-1700	YOK	YOK	YOK	VAR	HAYIR	OZEL	ILKOGRETIM	KANUNI TAKIP
ERKEK	EVLI	44-50	1701-2250	YOK	VAR	YOK	VAR	EVET	KAMU	UNIVERSITE	NORMAL ODEME
KADIN	BEKAR	23-29	4201-6028	YOK	YOK	YOK	VAR	HAYIR	KAMU	UNIVERSITE	NORMAL ODEME
ERKEK	EVLI	51-57	1701-2250	VAR	VAR	YOK	VAR	EVET	EMEKLI	ILKOGRETIM	NORMAL ODEME
ERKEK	EVLI	51-57	2251-2650	YOK	VAR	VAR	VAR	EVET	EMEKLI	ILKOGRETIM	NORMAL ODEME
ERKEK	EVLI	37-43	1701-2250	VAR	YOK	VAR	VAR	EVET	KAMU	LISE	NORMAL ODEME
ERKEK	EVLI	58-65	950-1700	YOK	VAR	YOK	VAR	EVET	EMEKLI	UNIVERSITE	NORMAL ODEME
KADIN	EVLI	44-50	1701-2250	VAR	YOK	VAR	VAR	EVET	OZEL	UNIVERSITE	NORMAL ODEME

Regulated data table after data conversion completed is also shown in Table 3.

D. Examination of categorical variables

Customers are given a number from 1 to 226. The customer number was not considered as a variable because it would affect the results of the analysis. The distribution of customers by variables is examined separately for each variable and the results are discussed below.

When the gender variable is examined, it is seen that 66,37% of men and 33,63% women. In other words, 150 of the total 226 customers are male and the remaining 76 are female.

E. Establishing the Model

It is possible to find the most suitable model for the defined problem by testing as many models as possible. Therefore, the stages of data preparation and model formation are a recurring process until the model is the best [1]. In this study, classification model is included. In order to evaluate the current situation, classification analysis was performed by decision tree algorithms.

F. Implementation of decision tree algorithms

After evaluating existing customers with decision tree algorithms were used to make inferences for future customers. For this purpose, QUEST, C&RT, C5.0, CHAID algorithms were applied in IBM SPSS Modeler and the results were evaluated.

Fig. 2 Illustration of quest decision tree

As a result of Quest algorithm analysis, monthly income is higher than 1701 - 2250 TL and the most important factor is monthly income. If the monthly income is greater than 2251 - 2650, we see that 100% of the customers pay normally. If monthly income is less than or equal to 2251 - 2650, customers are normally paid with 66.67%, and 89.47% of those who have the house have paid in the normal way. In addition, 58.82% of those who do not have a home are observed to have legal follow-up.

As with all algorithms, the purpose of the CRT algorithm is to establish the most accurate model. The accuracy of the model is determined by the ratio of correctly predicted records if the dependent variable is categorical and by mean error squares method if it is continuous [16].

Fig. 3 A decision tree with CRT algorithm

The monthly income of the customers with 2651 - 3350 TL, 3351 - 4200 TL and 4201 TL and above, is 100%. It is observed that customers in the 950 - 1700 TL, 1701 - 2250 TL and 2251 - 2650 TL income ranges pay 66,66% of their loans in the normal way. The most important variable after this variable is the age variable, while the age of the customers is 37 23 - 29, 30 - 36, 37 - 43 in. 66,66% of the customers in the other age range fall into the legal follow-up.

Fig. 4 C5.0 Decision tree for the classification of high school and university customers

The criteria effective for the classification of high school and university graduates with a monthly income of TL 2251 and TL 4201 are the monthly income of the customers, the age variable and the additional income. According to this, it is seen that 6351 - 4201 and 63 customers who paid monthly income were all paid in the normal way. It is revealed that 71.87% of the customers whose monthly income is between 2251 - 2650 TL normally pay their loans in the normal way. Another distinctive benchmark for customers with a monthly income of TL 2251 - 2650 was the age variable. Accordingly, 95% of customers in the 23 - 29, 30 - 36, 37 - 43 age range pay their loans without disruption. 66,67% of customers aged 44 and 66 are under legal follow-up. Besides, 100% of the customers who are in this age group and who have income paid their loans without disrupting their loans. 80% of the customers who do not have the income of the spouses have been followed legally.

Fig. 5 CHAID 950-1700 TL and 950-2250 TL income tree sub-decision tree

The criteria that are effective in the classification of customers with a monthly income of 950 - 1700 TL are the customers' bank customers and education levels respectively. According to this, it is seen that the customers pay their loans by 60% in the case of being a bank salary customer. If the customer is not a bank salary customer, 96.36% have not been legally liable to pay loans. The client is not a bank salary customer; however, the education level has been followed by a high level of 98.07% in high school or primary school. In the university, it was found that 33.33% of the students paid the customer loan in the normal way.

In a classification model, the error rate is calculated by dividing the number of events classified as false by the whole number of events, and by dividing the number of correctly classified events by the whole number of events [17].

Comparing \$C-Odeme with Odeme		
Correct	209	92,48%
Wrong	17	7,52%
Total	226	

Comparing \$R-Odeme with Odeme		
Correct	204	90,27%
Wrong	22	9,73%
Total	226	

Comparing \$R1-Odeme with Odeme		
Correct	200	88,5%
Wrong	26	11,5%
Total	226	

Comparing \$R2-Odeme with Odeme		
Correct	204	90,27%
Wrong	22	9,73%
Total	226	

Fig. 6 Analysis Results

The results of the decision tree algorithms used in the application are given in the Figure 6. According to this, the model with the highest share of accuracy is 92.48%.

III. RESULTS

This project included an application in the banking sector and evaluated the performance of individual loan customers. Within the scope of the study, classification analysis was performed for current loan customers. As a result of the analysis carried out with IBM SPSS Modeler, confidential information in the data was released and customers were grouped according to their behaviour. The distribution of the customers in the classification was evaluated according to all variables.

In order to ensure sustainable growth, businesses must engage in both new customer acquisition and retention of existing customers. According to research, the cost of acquiring a new customer is well above the cost of holding an existing customer. For this reason, the existing customers should be recognized and the loyal customer portfolio, which will provide a competitive advantage in the market for the enterprises, has been established.

In the decision tree algorithm part of the application, customers are classified with C5.0, C&RT, QUEST and CHAID algorithms and the rules are extracted with decision trees in order to make predictions for the future. According to Clementine outputs, algorithms were compared, and the best ratio was determined with the correct classification rate of % 92,48 of the C5.0 algorithm.

When the C5.0 algorithm is examined it is seen that the biggest impact on the payment status is monthly income. In other words, monthly income came to the fore as the first point to be taken into consideration in creating decision rules. In the C5.0 algorithm, it was observed that the variables were not used in terms of gender, child and marital status while the rule was taken according to the payment status. This situation shows that all three variables have no significant effect on the payment status which is the target variable. Credit customers are the second most important variable of the way they work, and it is seen that university graduates pay their loans at a high rate.

IV. DISCUSSION

When we take into consideration the loan repayment status of the customers, the first target variable is monthly income. It means that if the client gets a loan from the bank, we can say that we will look at his monthly income first. As an example, your monthly income in Turkey is one of the first factor that will affect your mortgage loan process.

The most important factor affecting the payment status is the educational status, and for the customers, this result can be evaluated as negative and the guarantor is requested to decrease the risk ratio. When the majority of university graduates pay their loans in the normal way, a positive return can be made to the loan customers' applications in a short period of time and special campaigns such as interest rate cuts can be organized to earn the loyalty of these customers.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, banks need to know their customers correctly and distinguish risky customers from others in order to survive for a long time by providing competitive advantage in the sector. With this study, by using classification algorithms from data mining methods, profiles of individual loan customers were calculated according to their payment performances and rules were set for future credit customers. In light of the data, it is aimed to decrease the rate of legal follow-up in retail loans.

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